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Experimental setup for motion capturing two humans jointly handling an object

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Abstract

In manual assembly, human motion capture is difficult. Reproducibly capturing two humans who are jointly handling a single part requires synchronization, communication between humans, and correcting deviations. This paper proposes an experimental setup to capture and analyze human motion data using an overhead light projector that dynamically and visually guides collaborating humans to initial and target positions. The experimental setup comprises full-body, hand-finger, and gaze-tracking sensors. Cyclic synchronization helps to reduce drift, correct position errors, and make the method easily reproducible and robust for collecting human motion data. The accuracy of object motion, which is handled by humans to execute a cooperative task, is assessed. Preliminary results show a promising output that can be scaled up for human-robot interactions using digital human models e.g., to evaluate collaboration actions and identify shared roles.

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1. Introduction

In manual assembly lines, such as those in the automotive industry, some tasks require two humans to collaborate to handle objects when high coordination and positioning accuracy due to size, weight, or geometric tolerance are necessary. Tasks such as handling a car's windshield by two people during assembly operation are real-world examples where collaborative object handling is crucial. For handling a car windshield (see Fig. 1), two workers may need to agree on how to move the object (windshield) from the initial to the target position. While moving the object, they should constantly adapt to their co-worker's motion behaviour. This requires both humans to imagine the potential trajectory, feel the action and reaction forces, and attentively follow the movement and intention of their co-worker [c. 14].

Planning the object handling process for two co-workers will avoid potential errors that may arise due to positioning misalignment, role conflict, and safety hazards [17]. Objects to be handled can be large, heavy, or difficult to handle by a single person; shared cooperation between two humans may also depend on the workplace setting that describes processes to lift, align, and position the part accurately. Thus, a reproducible experimental setup is necessary to investigate how two humans

understand each other and efficiently communicate when to lift the part, how to align it, and where to position it.

Such experimental setups are crucial for modelling two humans who jointly handle objects. For instance, planning manual operations, implementing position control, and human-robot collaboration scenarios. Here, human motion models preemptively plan how two humans will jointly perform handling tasks and transfer this knowledge for designing real human-robot collaboration for handling objects. In this respect, the quality and accuracy of captured human motion data are essential, especially for two humans. However, human motion capture data, particularly for two humans, is difficult due to the gap in reproducible experimental setups mainly designed for tracking human motions, eye gazes, and object positions. Classical motion capture systems exhibit calibration and synchronization problems when multiple humans cooperate and interact in a confined assembly space. These problems make it challenging to recreate realistic working conditions in lab environments, meaning that even if motion capture is used, the data might only partially represent what happens on an assembly line.

This work proposes a novel experimental setup to address the challenges in capturing human motion data. This setup incorporates motion capture systems such as finger, body, and gaze trackers to accurately capture human motion in collabora-

Fig. 1: Car windshield assembly process in shop floor environment. (Source: Skoda story board [https://www.skoda-storyboard.com/en/seriova-vyroba-skoda-octavia-1/], used with permission from Skoda Media Services)

tive tasks. By improving the human motion data, human-robot collaboration models can be better developed, and overall productivity in industries like automotive manufacturing can be enhanced.

2. Related Work

2.1. Physical setup feasibility analysis

In the experimental setup, conducting a feasibility analysis of the physical system and its configuration is required for its successful development. Physical feasibility analysis for the human motion capturing systems setups such as wearable or on-body-attached motion tracking systems (e.g. inertial measurement units (IMU), lighthouse-based systems, or marker-based optical sensors) that transfer human motions into a digital environment is crucial [18]. In such a physical setup, one of the main requirements to overcome the inherent challenges known in designing experimental setups for motion capturing of two humans. These challenges include ensuring sufficient motion quality [12], communication, and intention integration by clarifying whether humans use the passive intention observer models [16] or haptic channels [4]. Motion capturing setting up two independent systems requires device synchronization, including motion capture systems and other sensors such as eye tracker. In this respect, in [9], complex and sophisticated setups and protocols are proposed to ensure accurate and reliable data collection. The cost and practicality of using multiple motion capture suits or sets of sensors have been limited due to several factors such as cost, setup time, applicability, and feasibility [13].

Human-to-human collaboration involving physical object manipulation depends on the interaction of the humans with the object [17], communication [14] and also physical strains that arise due to pull-push [1] and speed incompatibility [7] effects. Focused on human communication for handling objects, [14] proposed a model for control strategy using the interaction forces as a communication channel to observe how humans co-

ordinate their actions. Since understanding this coordination is not inherent, interaction forces have been computed during a dual cooperative object manipulation.

Light projection approaches have been used to assist the workers in following a path or positioning the parts to be handed at specific locations. In [3], augmented process and object position information using visualized light projections on the workstation table was proposed. The workstation was composed of a projector mounted overhead of the workstation table, projecting colored shapes and semantic information on the surface, as well as 3D sensors that allow the observation and prediction of the motion behavior of humans. However, the design setup is developed for system architecture based on goal selection for each co-worker partner in contrast to sharing.

2.2. Synchronization in simultaneous motion capturing

Studies presented by [19] show that workers with similar physical and functional capabilities perform their tasks more efficiently than two workers with different physical and functional setups [19]. In [2], the collaborator's relationship and operational scheme based on symbiosis is emphasized, and the experiment is assessed for factors such as action, guidance, and protection. The evaluation metrics apply effort and speed for action, knowledge and decision-making for guidance, and safety and ergonomics are evaluated if they yield an impact on the collaborator's relationship.

Managing and processing the large volumes of data generated by motion capture systems, especially in real-time, requires robust systems that can handle synchronization and provide meaningful representations of movement [10]. Moreover, large data handling while dealing with challenges related to temporal synchronization, deviation correction, complex movements, device synchronization, cost and practicality requires a robust experimental setup [11]. This robust experimental setup should support advanced methodologies and technologies that are needed to improve the accuracy and reliability of synchronized motion capture data in interactive scenarios [e.g., 5].

The previous studies do not focus on set ups for jointly motion-capturing two humans. The human motion capture methods presented in [6] focus only on non-collaborative scenarios. The symbiosis relationship investigated in [2] does not take real collaborative tasks that share a common resource, goal, space and time.

The current study proposes a novel experimental setup that may help to overcome difficulties in synchronization, communication, and correction of deviation to collect accurate and reproducible human motion data for two humans collaboratively handling an object. This may improve procedures for accurate and reproducible human-robot motion-capturing and experimental setups for modelling human-robot interactions and robot control development. In general, recorded human motion is very complex because of the high degrees of freedom of the human body. Modelling human motion should comprise large variations in motion style and dynamics. To address this, human motion is defined by a low-dimensional feature vector (latent space) extracted from motion capture data. This latent space

representation shall be contributed with robot control model in future works. It enables the investigation of human motion and uses latent space control for human-robot collaboration (HRC).

3. Experimental Setup

A collaborative team of two participants within 1.80m and 1.83m height is created for an assembly task that involves manipulating a rigid object from one point (Location A) to another (Location B). The two participants maintain a standing position with their feet at fixed location throughout the task.

3.1. Layout planning and feasibility analysis

A digital twin environment that simulates the MVN motion capture in real-time is created in a game engine (i.e., Unity3D). This approach, with the video streams from the three cameras, is used to monitor the progress and provide real-time feedback to participants during the experimental test. An obtained result is shown in Figure 2a. This can help identify errors and artifacts through early intervention and suggest corrective actions by calibrating the system again. As shown in Figure 2b, the digital twin model integrates motion capture data from IMUs with a simulated human model.

The space used for the experimental setup is 4m in width, 6m in length, and 3.5m in height. The designed workplace consists of two distinct components: the table and the frame, as shown in Figure 2a. The table has specific dimensions: width: 1.1m, Length: 0.9m, and Height: 1.1m. The dimensions indicate that the table is relatively compact, with enough space for two participants to work together comfortably while handling an object.

The frame is designed to vertically support the mounted devices, projector and camera. The height of the frame is specified as 2.97m, which is suitable for mounting a projector to project a grid and markers on the table and mounting a camera to record a top view. The height of the frame is adjustable, which accommodates the mounted equipment for future research activities.

The experimental test requires four cameras to record activities. As shown in Figure 2a, Camera 2 overviews the experimental setup and captures participant and object interactions. Camera 3 records the object's movements from a top-down perspective. This view offers valuable insights into the spatial dynamics and trajectory of the object as it is manipulated and interacted with the participants. Additionally, Camera 3 is positioned to provide a detailed view of the object's movements from the front, complementing the top-down view provided by Camera 4. Camera 1 (optional) is an addition to the experimental setup positioned opposite Camera 2 along the y-direction. This multi-perspective approach enables detailed analysis and tracking of the object's behaviour during the experimental test. By combining various views from different angles, researchers can better understand the object's environment.

3.2. Physical setup

The real experimental layout (see the upper part of the Figure 2b) is designed in the Lab based on the simulated environment described in Subsection 3.1 to evaluate human-to-human collaboration for handling an object during an assembly task. The task involved participants manipulating a rigid object (Red Rod) from one designated point (picking location A) to another (placing location B), as indicated in Figure 2c. The detail of the humans jointly manipulating an object from the initial to the target positions is given in Section 1. The experimental setup involves installing and calibrating multiple sensors, including Xsens MVN (Link), VR Gloves (Manus Prime II), and an Eye tracker (Pupil Invisible). Additionally, three cameras are established to capture the activity from different angles. These cameras are proposed to assist manual and automated post-processing tasks such as motion segmentation. Such semantic labeling is crucial for assessing motion quality and for motion model creation in the later stages. During the preliminary tests, motion artifacts are observed in the MVN recorded motion capture data, which must be investigated to find the root causes. In this regard, video captures, and MVN motion data frames are synchronized and analyzed. Video records from different angles will enhance the coverage of the workspace and also sufficiently visualize participants' interaction with an object. All cameras are connected to one PC, and each camera frame is merged into partitioned windows. The output image frame is synchronized with the motion capture data frames. Furthermore, a projector is used to project object picking and placing locations with task markers onto the table, which guides the handling process, as depicted in Figure 2c.

Participants are given tasks such as reaching, grasping, lifting, moving and manipulating a rigid object, as shown in Figure 2b&c. These tasks need two main components: the rod object and the soft material, e.g., foam rubber. The length of the rod is fixed to 0.7m, considering the size of the table and the reachability for both participants. The radius of the rod is set to 1.5cm for optimal grasping comfort for both humans. Colouring the object, as shown in Figure 2c, is essential to facilitate easy monitoring, automatic detection and tracking of the object's movement during the experimental test. In addition, a yellow ring is added to help participants quickly locate the object and provide a focal point for eye-tracking sensors to track the object's movement more effectively. From the eye-tracking sensors, we are interested in gathering the focus point of the participant and its association with the motion between attention and the desired actions. Foam rubber helps for cushioning and enhancing grip while manipulating the object. Additionally, a V-notch is created on the surface of the foam rubber to prevent the rod from rolling on the table's surface. This feature ensures that participants can consistently grip and place the rod in the desired location.

3.3. Visual guiding constraints

For each experimental task, various sample locations on the table for the initial and final positions of the rigid object are

Fig. 2: Proposed experimental setup design sequence (a → d): (a) Layout planning using digital environment e.g., Unity3D, (b) Physical and digital twin, (c) Visual guide for randomly generated target positions, (d) Motion capturing process using MVN analyze.

required. A uniform random distribution is used to generate random sample points within the defined working space area. This distribution ensures an equal probability for each point on the table to be selected as a sample location. Selected sample points provide that the experiments cover diverse locations within the workspace. To ensure the validity of these sample locations, we consider the limitations identified from a reachable area within a working space that humans can physically reach. The reachable area is defined as the space that a human can reach while performing a task; this area sets constraints on the human's movement within their operational environments (see [8], page 159), which can manipulate the object. Understanding the limitations of both participants in achieving the task is essential. The digital twin model enables us to simulate human movements and their capabilities within the working space; this allows us to locate the reachable area that humans can reach, as illustrated in Figure 2c.

3.4. Motion capture, pre-processing and analysis

This study employs the Xsens MVN (MVN Link—240Hz), which includes 17 wired motion trackers (MTx). All motion trackers are combined with biomechanical models to obtain the positions and orientations of all human body segments (23 segments). Each body segment has all kinematic quantities represented within a standard local coordinate frame, which is a right-handed Cartesian coordinate system. In this system, the X-axis is positive when moving forward, the Y-axis is positive when moving laterally, and the Z-axis is positive when pointing upward [15]. MVN Studio is used to visualize the movements of the human and the object being handled in real-time or from previous recordings, as displayed in Figure 2d). During the experimental test, calibration is conducted to estimate the orientation of the sensors with respect to the corresponding segments, as well as the dimensions/proportions of the person being tracked. In addition, the gaze data allows the analysis of participants' visual focus. Before starting the experimental test, all participants were informed about the experimental procedures and provided their written informed consent.

The approaches for motion data processing and analysis describe the interaction between a human's motion in handling an object and understanding how humans behave while performing the task. The movement of both participants through sensor

tracking and the Euclidean distance between pick and place position is used for the purposes of the analysis.

4. Result

The experimental task of manipulating the object is repeated for 500 seconds (120000 Frames). To understand the object movements, the location (X, Y, Z) of both sensors (Props) (T1 and T2) for both participants (P1 and P2) are collected from the human motion data at each frame, and the result is presented in Figure 3a. T1 and T2 are the sensors fixed on the rigid object (Red-Rod-object) attached to the right-hand sensors of the first participant (P1) and left-hand of the second participant (P2), respectively. The actual distance between T1 and T2 is equal to 0.63m. The Figure 3a shows the object motion in two clusters (pattern) for P1 (plotted in blue) and P2 (plotted in red). The ends of the clusters represent the pick and place locations, and the route between the pick and place displays the object's trajectory.

To demonstrate how effectively participants collaborate their movements and maintain spatial relationships during the task, the Euclidean distance between T1 and T2 is calculated, and the obtained distribution of distances is presented in Figure 3b. The figure shows how frequently the participants maintained or exceeded a threshold distance during the task, a threshold distance equal to 0.63m in this scenario. The statistical analysis shows that the mean value is 0.636m, the data range is from 0.60m to 0.67m, and the standard deviation is 0.0123. The result presents how well participants synchronize their movements, particularly during task pick-and-place activities.

The time series data in Figure 3c illustrates the movements of both participants during this activity, highlighting the moments when each participant picks up an object, lifts it, and places it down. The maximum peaks indicate reaching a picking point, and the minimum peaks represent the placing points. Effective collaboration relies on synchronization, so examining the alignment of joint positions and movements for both participants is necessary. For this purpose, the time differences between participants to perform a task, the time taken by P1 minus the time taken by P2, are calculated. To explain the obtained results, the kernel density estimation (KDE) of the time differences is plotted as shown in Figure 3d. The figure demonstrates the time differences for each participant at peak points.

Fig. 3: Result visualizations and descriptions.

The analyses of deviations for the sensors' (T1 and T2) position along the Y-direction are performed as the humans coordinate their movements to manipulate the object. Participants are instructed to adjust their movements and use yellow-ring-markers on the manipulated object as reference points to promote better synchronization and communication throughout the test. The deviations of sensors are identified when the participant diverges from the expected path, which shows where the corrections are needed. The statistical analysis reveals that the mean deviation for T1 and T2 along the Y-direction is 0.0147m and 0.0110, respectively, and the standard deviation is 0.0183 and 0.0139. The results identify who pulls first to make a deviation and who follows, e.g., during the collaborative handling task, P2 pulls first to make a deviation with a count of 24,208

frames with a duration of 100.87 seconds, while P1 follows. However, P1 pulls the object with a count of 19,099 frames with a duration of 79.58 seconds, while P2 follows.

Motion capture can show how participants communicate non-verbally through their movements. For example, if one participant moves in a particular way, the other may respond by adjusting their position. Analyzing these interactions can emphasize how effectively individuals communicate non verbally during a task. Effective communication is reflected in the ability to adapt movements in response to the co-worker's actions, which can be measured by analyzing movement adjustments. For this purpose, the correlation analysis was implemented to find the strength and direction of the linear relationship between the participants' movements. The results reveal that the correlations are 0.97, 0.36, and 0.75 in the X, Y, and Z dimensions, respectively.

5. Discussion

The obtained motion capture data provide an understanding of participants' interactions during the pick-and-place collaborative task. The average distance between T1 and T2 for each participant at the pick and place position, defined by maximal and minimal peaks, is calculated (equal to 0.63m, see Figure 3a). Even with a high-quality capture process, it is observed that the motion data has fewer outliers, which mostly overestimates the object's trajectory during the test. The potential sources of outliers can be measurement noises, events, and networks. Manual calibration for offset drift in recorded motion data is performed based on the right-foot position.

During the task, participants collaborated effectively on their movements and maintained spatial relationships, as presented in Figure 3b. A tight distribution of distances around the threshold indicates satisfactory participants coordinate their movements. The Euclidean distance-based dataset has a narrow range (7cm) and small standard deviation, indicating the data points are tightly cumulated around the mean value, with very few outliers. The result illustrates effective spatial awareness and participant communication during the pick-and-place task.

The positive mean time difference for peaks (0.09, 0.21 sec), as displayed in Figure 3d, implies that P1 tends to reach their peaks after P2; this indicates that P2 is leading the movement. This means that P2 is likely initiating the movement first in this collaborative task, while the other adjusts their movements accordingly (following). P1 may have a longer reaction time, leading to delayed responses compared to P2. This can happen when one participant has a better visual or spatial awareness, allowing them to initiate movements more effectively, and the follower may synchronize their actions according to the leader's movements. Differences in physical capabilities, experience, or task understanding between participants may also influence who leads and who follows.

By addressing the deviations, participants can enhance their performance in collaborative tasks, leading to more efficient and successful collaborations. The results of computing deviations for the sensors' (T1 and T2) position along the Y-direction

indicate that humans coordinate their movements effectively to manipulate the object. From the presented statistical analysis, the position of sensors (T1 and T2) is slightly movement toward the position of P2. Furthermore, the standard deviation in the Y-direction demonstrates reasonable variability in Y-positioning. The results emphasize considerable variability that may require enhanced communication and synchronization processes for improved coordination during collaborative tasks. Based on the obtained results, P2 often initiated the action during the collaborative handling task, which led to deviations that made P1 follow by pushing the object. Concentrating P2 in pulling implies a leadership role in the task, while the movement of P1 to push indicates a supportive role. This cooperative dynamic highlights the importance of synchronized actions in teamwork, emphasizing how each individual's contributions complement the other to manage the object effectively.

Correlation analysis was conducted to determine the strength and direction of the linear relationship between the participants' movements. A high correlation in the X direction (0.97) indicates a strong relationship, where when one participant moves left or right, the other adjusts their position accordingly. This implies effective communication and coordination between the participants during the task. However, the Y direction shows a weaker correlation (0.36), indicating less synchronization in forward and backward movements. This may be due to less effective communication or individual movement strategies. A considerable correlation (0.75) in the Z direction indicates that participants adapt well to each other's movements in an upward/downward direction to maintain the integrity of their collaborative task. The higher correlations in the X and Z directions imply strong communication through movement, as participants closely monitor and respond to each other's actions to improve the overall performance of the task. In contrast, the adjustments in forward/backward movements are less coordinated and indicate areas where communication could be improved.

6. Conclusions and Future Work

A reproducible experimental setup is designed and implemented to capture motion data during collaborative object handling in assembly processes concerning human-to-human interactions. The findings highlight the importance of movement-based communication. The research is extending to be better for accuracy and reproducibility of human-human motion capturing and for experimental setups modelling human-robot interactions and robot control development.

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